

Towards robotization of foraging wild fruits under canopy - A multi-camera drone-borne berry mapping

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Abstract. The rapid technological advancements are allowing not only the automatization of work, but often also its facilitation through human-robot collaboration. This topic is investigated in the FEROX project, which addresses the underexplored domain of improving the process of wild berry harvesting in Northern European forests with robotics and AI. This paper investigates the integration of multi-camera drone technology for under-canopy mapping in the context of wild berry location mapping. Our proposed methodology lays a groundwork for utilizing AI methods to provide georeferenced maps of berries' locations in forest areas, inherently characterized by an unreliable GNSS signal. We carry out initial tests in a forest in eastern Finland with a custom hexacopter, proving the suitability of our approach for retrieving a geographical position of detected fruits with the tested sensor configuration, enabling further processing to supply foragers with wild fruit yield heat maps on a per-species basis.

Keywords: UAV, robotics, visual SLAM, 3D, wild fruit, foraging.

1 Introduction

Drones, or unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), and AI are gradually revolutionizing our practices, offering various advantages for daily practices, reducing efforts and providing undeniable benefits. In the context of Northern European forests, where wild fruits like blueberries and cloudberries grow abundantly, these technological advancements hold great promise. However, despite the natural abundance, it is estimated that less than 10% of the total annual wild berry yield is harvested from these forests. The main challenge in collecting wild berries lies in the manual harvesting, namely pickers' working conditions. Due to short seasons, most of the work is conducted by foreigners with limited knowledge of the language, practices and the area [1]. Previous studies examining the feasibility of providing berry yield maps to support pickers have underscored the need to carry out a practical pilot study [2]. The EU FEROX¹ project aims

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to develop innovative solutions based on the integration of drones, AI, computer vision and 3D mapping to monitor harvesting activities in under canopy environments. In the long term, this will incorporate improvements in the working conditions of berry pickers and mitigate the risk factors and threats to their safety during berry picking activities.

2 Related works

UAVs have found extensive applications among professionals and enthusiasts across diverse industries, including construction, city planning, cultural heritage preservation, mining, and geology [3]. While the autonomy of flight in open areas with reliable access to GNSS-RTK positioning has reached a mature state, more intricate environments, such as under canopy flights in the forests, still present formidable challenges.

Several studies have delved into the exploration of deploying drones beneath forest canopies. The predominant method for mapping and navigation involves the use of LiDAR sensors. Hyypä et al. [4] introduced an approach to forest mapping using a commercial simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) for extracting valuable information for forest inventory purposes. Wang et al. [5] extended the work by incorporating a high-quality Riegl LiDAR into the methodology. Tian et al. [6] employ LiDAR sensors in collaborative SLAM, but for the main purpose of navigating a UAV fleet during search and rescue operations.

Conversely, several studies have explored visual sensors in mapping forests from the under-canopy. Krisanski et al. [7] conducted an analysis of tree diameter measurements based on images captured using a small UAV. Similarly, Zhang et al. [8] investigated the potential use of 3D reconstruction results of drone-based imagery for biomass measurements. Notably, both studies employed manually flown drones and processed the data using Agisoft Metashape [9].

3 Proposed methodology

3.1 Data processing pipeline

In this paper, we propose a novel data processing pipeline for obtaining berry yield maps. The method utilizes a drone, equipped with 2 stereo cameras and a GNSS-RTK receiver.

In the first step, COLMAP-SLAM² [10,11] is used for processing the high-frequency front-facing stereo images. Based on matching of stereo pairs, the camera trajectory is retrieved. Then, camera timestamps are matched using the nearest neighbor approach to the timestamps of GNSS positions. All positions obtained with too low precision are discarded. A 2D Helmert transformation is used to transform the front-facing camera trajectory from local to global coordinate frames.

² https://github.com/3DOM-FBK/COLMAP_SLAM

In the next step, the external orientation parameters of both stereo cameras are employed to transform the georeferenced set of forward-looking camera poses into the poses of the downward-facing camera. The parameters for this transformation are assumed to be known from the field calibration. This step is necessary due to the low overlap of the nadir images. A nearest neighbor approach is used, once again, to match the timestamps of the front- and down-facing cameras. Finally, the georeferenced nadir images are transferred to Agisoft Metashape [9], where the generation of an orthomosaic is carried out. The results can be used to apply AI-based methods to obtain the location of berries, either directly from the subset of the orthomosaic, or by performing the detection on single images and finding the corresponding position in the orthomosaic.

3.2 Drone setup

For testing the proposed methodology, a custom hexacopter *Scout* developed by Ingeniarius Lda (Fig. 1) has been employed. The drone is equipped with 2 ZED X stereo cameras (nadir- and front-facing), an RTK-enabled Emlid Reach GNSS receiver, an inertial measurement unit, Pixhawk flight controller and onboard Jetson Orin AGX with Robot Operating System (ROS; [12]) Noetic for data collection. To ensure stable frames, they were limited to 15Hz and 0.5Hz for the front- and down-facing cameras.

Fig. 1. Custom drone *Scout* developed by Ingeniarius Lda (left). View from a front-facing stereo camera of the drone inside the forest (right).

4 Experiments

4.1 Data

Data were collected during the summer field work in June 2023 in Iломantsi, in eastern Finland (Fig. 2) with the *Scout* UAV presented in Section 3.2. For the purpose of testing the data processing pipeline, a sequence with 2,081 stereo-pairs from the forward-looking camera and 234 stereo pairs from the nadir camera was collected. In total, 171 valid GNSS positions were used: the rest (around 95%) have not passed the quality control criteria of fixed position with a horizontal precision at most equal to 1 m.

4.2 Results

The drone trajectory and a sparse point cloud of tie points can be seen in Fig. 2. Notably, tree trunks are clearly identifiable, without shadowing effects of odometry errors, despite a complex trajectory.

Fig. 2. A sparse point cloud and the front-facing camera trajectory (in red) reconstructed with COLMAP-SLAM [11]: an orthographic top view (left) and close-up view (right).

Then, the georeferencing procedure has been performed. The root mean squared error (RMSE) of the 2D alignment between the trajectory and sparse GNSS positions was equal to 1.8m, which, considering the cutoff of 1 m for the GNSS position precision, was deemed acceptable. In the next step, an orthomosaic was generated (Fig. 3) and a berry detection was simulated. Since the AI models for fruit detection are not yet available, a pair of berries are annotated by hand on the image to showcase the berry geolocation function of the workflow (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3. Orthomosaic generated in Agisoft Meshape.

Fig. 4. Example results of the proposed pipeline. Berry locations marked on the nadir drone image (left) and their respective positions in a global reference frame on an orthomosaic (right).

5 Conclusions

In this study, a novel pipeline for UAV data processing has been established, enabling the creation of georeferenced wild fruit maps based on under-canopy surveys. An example dataset obtained in a Finnish forest during the summer season has been processed and the workflow has been successfully tested. In further developments, focus will be on integrating the described methodology with AI-based fruit detection models. Additionally, further tests will be conducted with an improved hardware setup to select optimal data acquisition parameters and verify the robustness of the method on different datasets.

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